

Welcome to the qualitative survey on the use and further development of persistent identifiers (PIDs) in Germany.

Thank you for your interest and for taking the time to participate in this survey.

As part of the DFG-funded research project “PID Network Germany,” [506475377](https://doi.org/10.5064/75377), on the current and future use of persistent identifiers in Germany, we would like to engage in dialogue with you, stakeholders from PID registration agencies, aggregators, citation databases, and infrastructure initiatives, through this online survey. This survey aims to gain a well-founded understanding of the current status, your existing needs, supply gaps, and development potential in addressing PIDs.

Participation is voluntary.

The following questions serve as a guide. Free text fields allow you to describe your experiences and perspectives in detail. There are no “right” or “wrong” answers—your individual perspective is particularly valuable to us.

We would be delighted to publish your answers as a PDF document, along with the evaluation, on [Zenodo.org](https://zenodo.org).

No participation

For publishing:

Consent

No consent

Anonymous

With name, ORCID iD if applicable

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7604-8041>

Organization/Institution: ARK Alliance

Date: 2025.11.19

If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to contact me, Andreas Czerniak (andreas.czerniak@uni-bielefeld.de), at any time. In addition, we, the PID Network Project Team (info.pidnetwork@listserv.dfn.de), will be happy to assist you with any questions you may have regarding PIDs, both in a national and international context.

I’m immensely grateful for your assistance.

1. Status Quo and Utilization

Archival Resource Keys (ARKs) are a kind of "persistent identifier" (PID), used in a similar way to DOIs, Handles, PURLs, and URNs. ARKs offer a free, open, and flexible way for organizations to create long-lasting links to their digital resources, helping to keep information accessible over time. They are especially affordable for organizations that require millions of PIDs or that have limited budgets. ARKs, like all PIDs, follow a very similar structure. They share one URL pattern (<https://> + resolver + name authority + name) and one technical trick, namely, the simple web redirection built into all web software since 1993 and offered for free by hundreds of URL shorteners.

Since 2001, approximately 12.3 billion ARKs have been created by over 1700 organizations, including 12 national libraries, 215 universities, 254 archives, 144 museums, 124 journals, and 59 scientific centers. Some of the major users are the Internet Archive, Portico, the French National Library, the Louvre, the Smithsonian, the British Library, and the University of California. Initially, the main ARK users were cultural heritage institutions, however, more recently, there has been significant interest in using ARKs for scholarly outputs in repositories and journal publications because of their flexibility and low cost.

Like DOIs, ARKs support research and scholarship, however ARKs come with no fees, no limits on how many you can create, and no metadata requirements. From the beginning, ARKs were decentralized and could be used to identify any kind of thing (digital, physical, or abstract). DOI's, in contrast, were created by large commercial publishers to control academic knowledge linking infrastructure. Unlike ARKs which can be used by anyone for free, DOIs burden content creators with ongoing fees and service dependencies. This is why ARKs are being considered by many as an alternative to DOIs.

2. Infrastructure and Services

The ARK infrastructure consists of standards and best practices linked from the [ARK Alliance](#) website, the [N2T.net](#) resolver, and the [registry of ARK organizations](#).

PIDs are just permalinks that contain a substring that makes them recognizable in the wild. Like any permalink, some PIDs may offer a metadata store (eg, DataCite), but none

of them are guaranteed. Even as “aspirational” identifiers, however, permalinks and PIDs have a better chance of surviving than the average URL, which breaks in 100 days. ARKs are flexible, low-cost PIDs for citing any kind of resource.

Organizations that wish to use ARKs can [request a Name Assigning Authority Number \(NAAN\)](#) for their organization, decide what ARK features to use, and modify their website to accept URL paths containing their NAAN (e.g., a server configuration line that accepts “ark:12345”). Then they choose whether to publicize their ARKs based at their own website’s domain (their local resolver) or N2T.net (the global resolver). N2T, which was built for ARKs, also knows how to resolve hundreds of compact identifier schemes, such as Protein Databank and ChEBI identifiers (developed in partnership with [identifiers.org](#)).

3. Needs and Wishes

At the moment, the ARK infrastructure is hosted by the California Digital Library. Over the last five years, ARKs have experienced substantial growth in their adoption across scholarly and cultural heritage communities. This has led to a pressing need for less dependence on any single organization and a more formal operational and governance structure for the ARK Alliance in order to judiciously manage the ARK infrastructure on behalf of its growing user community.

ARK infrastructure hosted by the California Digital Library (CDL)

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| <p>Includes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NAAN registration, for orgs to start using ARKs • N2T.net (Name-to-Thing), the global ARK resolver <p>But ARKs are <i>decentralized</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1700 local ARK resolvers • Most ARKs don’t use the global resolver <p>ARK spec and documentation are maintained by the ARK Alliance at https://arks.org</p> |
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Our wishlist includes the following.

1. Run a number of resolver replicas. The ARK resolver infrastructure runs inside two small Docker containers, easily hosted in locations distributed globally.
2. A very simple shared metadata store that ARK implementers could use to create a secondary copy of their metadata. This would offer additional preservation assurance.

4. Recommendations

Support open infrastructures that offer an alternative to the de facto scholarly publishing ecosystem, which is expensive and leaves researchers without a meaningful role in governing their own research.

Funders, research institutions, libraries, data centers, archives, and museums can organize and collectively sustain such alternatives.